

Sensors and ICT/ IoT to assess wellbeing in managing livestock and to inform the value chain

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Introduction

For centuries there has been a process of human observation of animals and crops by producers that results in a plan (schedule) to take action by the use of equipment. There has always been an incentive to reduce required labour with most recent the use of milking robots and autonomous tractors and roughage feeding machines.

Human observation was not possible for some important characteristics like soil chemical properties and the composition, eventual contamination of milk. Taking samples and sending them to a laboratory became practise and resulted in milk and soil property values determined following well described protocols. Appropriate measures could be taken by relatively simple decision rules.

With the introduction of cheap electronics, advanced sensing techniques and information and communication technology, ICT and increased processing power, it is possible to develop sensor technology to observe properties of crops, soils, animals and produce. This results in much more data which requires advanced data analyses, predictive models and decision support systems. We are now in the process of integrating all those sensors, processes and automated systems under regularly changing names like Computer Integrated Agriculture, Precision Agriculture, M2M, Smart Farming and Farming 4.0. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. An overview of processes and objects in modern agricultural production.

Animal welfare is defined by Botreau et al. (2007) as good feeding, good housing, good health and appropriate behaviour. These criteria are specified by a number of sub criteria. One could add to this no aggression between animals.

Lucky enough, most of the factors determining the level of wellbeing also determine productivity of animals and the quality of their produce, so there is also an economic incentive. However scientific based criteria are not necessarily what is accepted by the public. Especially housing, the abundant use of medicines, side effects in respect of pollution and just the size of holdings are criticised. This public pressure requires that the whole production chain can deliver proof of responsible animal husbandry. The mentioned technology is essential to deliver that proof.

Sensors

The first application of sensors is direct process control of equipment like controlling vacuum of milking machines, climate control and dosing of fertilizers and spraying fluids. The second application is the observation of properties of crops, soils, animals and produce.

We want property values with a meaning for control of production process, but these are often not direct measurable on an efficient or practical way. Sensors observe physical properties that are technically feasible at acceptable cost or effort and which have shown a relation with the properties of relevance. A clear example is the spectral reflection of feed which will give estimates for feed properties like moisture and protein content. To establish those relation we still need the chain of samples and laboratory analyses for a fraction of the observations.

Radio Frequency Identification, RFID, systems were the trigger for what is now Precision Livestock farming. They made it possible to identify individual animals and the ISO standards 11784 and 11785 with their compliance test guarantee uniqueness of the sensor Id such that they can be used for international tracking of animals.

The Global Navigation Satellite Systems, GNSS, is an important positioning technology at present widely used in precision agriculture with varying accuracies from several meters to centimetres. Energy requirement limit at present the use for positioning of free ranging animals. Another limitations is that the system cannot be used indoors. An alternative is positioning based on communication systems like Wifi, Bluetooth and 802.15.4. This requires a number of transceivers on known fixed locations. By measuring the transmission time it is possible to determine the position of the transceiver on the animal. The use of Ultra Wide Band, UWB, gives much higher accuracy. Systems marketed as Cow Positioning and CowView use this principle. It is also possible to determine a position by dead reckoning from accelerometer signals (Bidder et al. 2015). This also requires much energy and has the problem of error accumulation, which makes combination with another system to determine true position necessary. As accelerometers are also used in sensor systems to determine activity and behaviour of animals it is a not to neglect possibility. Positioning is also possible by cameras mounted above the animals, though this is more suited to determine movement of groups of animals. Accelerometer based systems mounted on animal legs or in a collar on the neck is used to determine animals activity, mounted on the tail of a cow it can indicate calving. Activity of a particular part of the animal is also possible by measuring stretch.

Body temperature measurement of animals gives information on their health Direct contact temperature measurement can be by injected intelligent transponders, in the reticulum or rumen through a bolus, rectal, in the abdo cavity, the eardrum, vaginal, artery bladder, pinal, digestive tract, jugular vine, gizzard, forehead (Sellier et all, 2014), or with a wireless sensor attached to the tail of a calf (Nogami et all 2014). Indirect measurement is mostly based on infra-red, IR. Locations to measure are eardrum, eye, cheek, nose, back, flank, hoofs, foot, skin, vulva pina, udder, legs, thigh, crest and comb.

Pulse rate of animals can be measured by a pulse oximeter incorporated in an ear tag or as a microchip implant, which measures also blood oxygen saturation. Pulse can also be measured by a belt as developed by Polar to measure the pulse of horses while training.

Measurement of respiration gives also an indication of animals health. IC4 technologies developed a collar with two Ultra Wide band radar receivers and transmitter antennas, which are able to measure the change in corpus which is proportional with respiration.

Analyses of breath is possible by laser spectroscopy and gas chromatography. pH of the rumen is measured by a bolus, incorporating a Ion Sensitive Field Effect Transistor, ISFET sensor. Electric conductivity in milk is an indication for mastitis.

Research efforts are made to measure sodium levels in sweat and other substitutes like potassium, lactate and glucose eventually combined with measuring skin temperature.

Biosensors work with the help of a recognition element and a transducing device. The recognition element works on the mechanism of affinity-pairing, such as enzyme/substrate and antibody/antigen receptors. The transducer detects any contact between such pairs by producing detectable electrical signals in response to biological activity. The technique of Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) can be used to detect influenza virus A in poultry, clenbuterol and ractonamine.

Microfluidics technology is able to utilize small samples, which can be quickly detected and lead to less reagent wastage. The technology is also used to detect subclinical ketose. Integration of microfluidics and fluorescent labels ensures not only the requirement of minimum sample volume, but also an enhancement in sensitivity by successfully reducing the background signal noise.

Quantum dots (QD) are utilized to provide stability. It has an extensive emission wavelength, which can be adjusted by changing their size and composition with other nanomaterials. Gold nanoparticles in combination with screen-printed electrodes have found their application in antibiotic detection. Impedimetric immunosensors is another highly sensitive and fast way to detect biomarkers and analytes of interest. Surface Plasmon resonance, SPR, gives highly sensitive results for antibiotic detection in chicken muscle/blood serum in slaughterhouses. The technique detects larger families of antibiotics and is also able to detect catalase in milk. Service Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy, SERS, uses the intrinsic vibrational fingerprint of analytes to detect molecules and can be used to detect bacteria. The use of biosensors in practise is limited by environmental factors influencing the sensing element. Implanted bio-nano sensors are used to detect metabolites like glucose, lactate, glutamate and adenosine. This can be combined with an implanted RFID device.

Measuring sound in animal houses is also a kind of activity measurement or can give an indication of respiratory problems.

Sensitive ground plates which measure the extended force are used to indicate lameness of cows.

Sensors to measure productivity of animals depend on the production factor to measure. Weight of animals was in the past estimated from easy to measure characteristics like height, length and chest girth of animals but is more objectively determined by weighing scales. This requires incorporation of the scale in the movement pattern of the animals. For poultry specific systems are developed from which some should be combined with a vision system to count the number of animals on the scale. Also vision techniques are used to estimate weight, where the old estimation formulas can form a basis. The quantity of milk is an essential property for breeders and the development of meters is quite old, with ICAR conformance tests to guarantee their accuracy. Also properties like protein and fat are measured with bio sensors. Temperature of milk will have a relation with body temperature. Somatic cell count is done with optical techniques. Counting and grading of eggs is used to measure productivity of poultry. Measuring the feed intake of individual animals can be done in feed stations by back weighing of remaining feed. For pigs and especially poultry this can only be done on the group level. Individual uptake of roughage is only measured in experimental farms and requires even there much attention.

Measurement of environmental factors like temperature and humidity can be done by existing sensor systems, though the latter is difficult due to the aggressive atmosphere in animal houses. Environmental regulations require the measurement of other properties like ammonia and dust.

Crop canopy sensors are used by farms that grow their own feed to manage grazing and cutting of grass it is important to have an estimate of the actual biomass and preferably also some quality variables. Estimation of biomass by a plate meter is already practised for a long time and supplied with electronics the results can automatically be recorded. Canopy height measurement by sonar or light beams are an alternative. Remote sensing techniques require a high resolution to realise a good estimate of total biomass and when applied as multi spectral, it is possible to estimate also a number of feed quality

variable values. Several techniques are used to estimate biomass and eventual other properties on harvesting machinery. Near InfraRed, NIR, is to estimate moisture and other properties on choppers. The same technique is used to estimate properties of applied manure. Soil moisture sensors are valuable for irrigation purposes. Differences in soil properties can be measured with electric conductivity.

Communication of data from sensor and measuring systems

Techniques for communication of sensor signals depend on where the conversion and processing of sensor signals take place and also where the sensor or its processor is located; i.e. fixed with access to an infrastructure or mobile as for example mounted on free moving animals. Analogue communication of the raw sensor signal becomes less as wires are always vulnerable in an environment with animals and mobile machinery. Processors become so small that analogue digital conversion and to a certain extent interpretation can take place near the sensor itself. In an infrastructure and on equipment analogue wires can be replaced by one serial industrial communication bus. What we observe up to now is that in spite of some initiatives a standard for communication of data in farm buildings is not realised. This contrary to Mobile equipment where a large number of manufacturers developed ISO11783, also known as ISOBUS. There are a number of industrial communication standards to choose of. These are RS232, RS422, RS423, RS458, CAN, Profibus, Modbus, Ethernet and many others.

Wireless communication is the only possibility when sensors are connected to animals and it is an attractive alternative for wires in a vulnerable environment. Wireless communication can be categorised in 1) Personal area network, PAN with as examples Bluetooth (802.15.1), NFC, RFID, 802.11n, 802.11ac, 2) Local area network, LAN, with as example Wifi, 802.15.4 (Zigbee, 6LowPAN), Z-Wave, 802.11af, 802.11ah and 3) Wide area network, WAN, with 2G (GSM), 3G, 4G (with LTE-M), 5G, Lora, Sigfox and Weightless. Wireless communication requires a waveband in which it communicates and there we can distinguish between licensed wavebands like used for 2G, 3G, 4G and 5G. One depends on the services of providers which hold the license in a particular region. The alternative are free bands as used by 802.15.4, Bluetooth, Lora, sigfox and Wifi.

For communication it is important to keep the seven layer ISO-OSI model in mind. It distinguishes seven different functionalities of communication from layer 1, the physical environment up to layer 7, the application layer. Above mentioned communication protocols define one or more of those layers. Standards for agriculture can choose one or a combination of those protocols. An example is where 802.11 is chosen for the physical and transport layers (1&2), TCP/IP for the Network, Transport and session layer (3-5), JSON for the presentation layer (6) and REST for the application layer (7). For sensors 802.15.4 is a logical choice for 1&2, and IP for 3, UDP for 4 and DDS for 5, but from there onwards it is up to agriculture to choose or develop a presentation and application layer. When energy saving is a concern, one should reconsider IP due to its long addressing space and look for a compact binary representation of the data like done in ISO11783. In selection of the wireless physical layer there is a weighting between the distance to cover and the required bandwidth. Distance is determined by frequency; low frequency is long distance; allowed power. Bandwidth by frequency; high frequency is high bandwidth, and by allowed duty cycle. When radio signals have to pass body tissue, as is the case for implants and boluses, a low frequency is required. Use of 124 KHz was much better than 433 Mhz as used in earlier experiments. (Goense et al. 2009).

It will stay responsibility of agriculture to define on top of the seven communication layers the definition of the data classes, its attributes and the relation between, those classes.

Short ranges can be overcome with mesh hopping protocols. Mesh hopping WIFI routers coming now in the market might become popular on farm yards, and when energy saving versions of the protocol become available, also to connect our fields.

The free bands cause a potential problem, as with the increasing popularity of IoT it can become crowded in some frequency bands. We have to realise that IoT for building and domotica, for equipment and installations and sensors on animals operate in the same farm building. When those applications all use 802.15.4 in the 2.4 GHz (WIFI) band, the possibility of interference will increase. In Europe there is only one channel available in the 868-868.6 range. The choice is between the free frequencies and licensed frequencies like 2G, 4G and 5G from providers with guaranteed performance.

UHF transponders operate in two frequency ranges — 902-928 MHz and 865-868 MHz, but Brazil does not allow 907.5 – 915 MHz. In Europe this band is separated from the free frequencies to use for WPAN like 802.15.4 which are above 868 MHz, but in the USA they share bandwidth. In spite of the fact that Yoon and Jang (2013) found a limited reduction in WPAN performance, farmers should be well aware of the consequences of utilizing UHF RFID systems.

Conversion of sensor signals

Sensors measure physical characteristics of the sensor element like voltages and currents which must be converted to data that have an agronomical meaning. This requires nearly always calibration of the measuring system. Maintaining data on calibration activities is important for correct calculation of properties. A correct measured and calibrated physical property has in many cases no agronomical or veterinary meaning. A clear example is the reflection of feed in several wave bands. These sensor values require analyses to find a correlation with for example moisture or protein content. Analyses of feed samples in a laboratory following the traditional way is required to establish such a relation and due to some unknown factors, there will always be a certain level of uncertainty. The combination of sensors which measure different physical properties is a way to reduce this problem. The technique of measuring must be well specified and environmental conditions should also be recorded. The advantage of all those sensor technologies even with their uncertainty is that we have objective measurements when compared to human observation.

Interpretation of sensor signals

Measured properties on animals or their environment are seldom information as such. A too high body temperature is a clear sign that something is wrong. A vaginal thermometer can be used to indicate calving by a cow. However Lind et al. (2016) reported that this was not in the benefit of wellbeing of the animal. Often analyses over a time series is required. Change in body temperature can indicate pregnancy and unexpected changes in body weight indicate health problems.

Acceleration of mounted sensors can be analysed and converted to categories of activities, like eating, walking, standing, resting. Deviation in the distribution of these activities can be interpreted as a disease or oestrus. Deviation in time spent on licking salt is an indication for ruminal acidosis.

Deviations from the distribution of broilers as measured by vision systems is an indication of a number of possible failures in the infrastructure (feeding supply, water supply, electricity) or human activity. Vision techniques together with different algorithms are also used to detect lameness of cows.

Lameness detection can be done by single, dedicated sensors like pressure sensitive ground plates, vision technology with specific algorithms and interpretation of accelerometers on one or more legs of the cow. An alternative is sensor fusion of sensors and data which are already present on many farms. De Mol et al (2013) were able to predict lameness with an overall sensitivity of 86% and specificity of 89% by combining lying behavior, milk yield and feeding data in the form of concentrate left-overs in the milking robot. Detection of early lameness is still difficult (van Nuffel et al. 2015)

A complication in animal husbandry is that a number of characteristics of animals are difficult to quantify. An example is lameness of cows. What is the definition of lameness and when is it mild or severe. Locomotion scores on a scale of 0 to 5 by trained professionals are used in research studies. Apart from the influence/bias of the observer, there is also difference in which score is judged as lame. Early detection is a challenge

Sound analyses can detect coughing of animals, which on its turn is an indication for respiratory problems/diseases. A challenge is to identify the animal which is coughing in an animal group. A combination with video detection to measure simultaneous body movement of coughing seems to work. (Kim et al 2015). Sound is also used to detect stress of poultry. The frequency of the sound produced by broilers has potential as an early warning for growth retardation. (Vranken 2016)

Above mentioned interpretation of sensor signals indicate the condition of animals and can be followed by immediate action. An example is the service of the Dutch-Flemish breeding cooperative CRV, which supports dairy farmers in insemination decisions for cows. Pedometers have taken over the detection of heat. CRV developed an app that not only signals this status but also suggests sperm from three

preferred bulls. As most farmers always choose option A of the list of three, they can now subscribe to a service where CRV automatically delivers the sperm, if not in stock with the farmer already.

Big-data and datamining

The expression Big-Data covers a wide range of activities in handling data. Sometimes just storing data in the cloud, the use of IoT technology, with reference to *Figure 1*, I would restrict Big-Data to those situations where data of many objects and/or many observations are brought together for further analyses where classical analyses software is not able to handle the amount of data. An example is the accelerations measured in three axes on a sensor mounted to an animal. A sampling frequency of 10 Hz results in a large amount of data and this data combined with observations of the behaviour of the animal will result in rules how behaviour can be determined by such sensors. On a higher level we can collect data on activity, amount of milk, milk temperature, body temperature, feed uptake, etc. Combined with observations on heat, rules can be established to predict heat without the need for human observation.

The difference between Big-Data and interpretation is not always that clear. With the present technology it is possible to follow behaviour of animals continuously. When this data is combined with health treatment of animals it will learn about effectivity of such treatments, certainly when this data can be obtained from a large number of farms.

Predictive modelling

Predictive modelling differs in so far from Big-Data that there is a clear idea of the processes that take place and that the input and output variables determining the behaviour of the described process are to a certain extent known.

Cows vary individually in the effectiveness of concentrate feed, though it is complex as there is substitution with the uptake of forage. Dynamic feeding estimates the actual individual milk yield response to concentrate intake by using an adaptive dynamic linear model. The response curve is derived from a mechanistic model for milk production and can be established empirically from daily milk yield development during early lactation when concentrate supply increase is linear (Andre et al., 2009)

Another example is a model to estimate the feed efficiency of dairy cows based on genotypic and phenotypic data and a model to predict the feed intake of cows. (Kempenaar et al. 2016). On a more global level there is a model to predict the profitability of dairy farms. (Yli-Heikkilä et al. 2015). Predicting pasture growth is important for management of grazing and harvesting. For the long run statistical models can be used, but with availability of long term weather predictions descriptive models become useful. (McCall and Bishop-Hurley, 2003).

Another example is the prediction of food path dermatitis of broilers. The time that the temperature humidity index is out of a certain comfort zone proved to be a good predictor of the percentage of broilers with FPD. (Vranken 2016)

Decision support

The results of laboratory analyses, converted sensor signals, big data analyses and predictive models, supplemented with external data sources, preferably by means of open data, are used to take decisions. Dynamic Feeding is an example of a decision support system which uses the estimated individual milk yield response to concentrate intake, together with data on the price of milk and concentrate feed. "Beregenen op maat", an irrigation decision support system, which uses apart from predicted forage growth with and without irrigation also the actual feed stock and the estimated purchase price of forage and resale price of milk and cows.

Equipment, actuators and robots

Mechanisation, automation and robotization is an ongoing development in animal husbandry. The latter two requires sensors for control of the process itself and delivers by that already an infrastructure for data handling on the equipment, but often also property values with agronomical meaning. Clear examples are automatic feeding systems, equipment for climate control and the milk tank. Equipment not only replaces labour or take care of animals comfort. The amount of Dust in broiler houses and ammonia in animal houses in general can be controlled/influenced by ventilation activity. (Vranken 2016). Robots, from which the milking robot is a prominent one, require additional sensors to replace the human observations.

One application which is not directly seen as equipment or a robot is virtual fencing. Positioning is a crucial sensor component for those systems. A limiting factor is energy requirement for those systems. More efficient GNSS receivers, alternatives for GNSS and energy scavenging systems will play a role.

Traceability

Governmental organisations or retailers require traceability of the whole food chain. Identification of individual animals plays an important role in the meat and dairy sector. It requires however also registration of birth, transfer and death of animals. An example is the Botswana Animal Identification and Traceability System, which is a farmer oriented system to organise compliance with European traceability requirements. It allows the farmer to tag their own cattle, effect ownership transfers, submit application for movement permit, report mortality, process replacement of lost ear tags, transfer ear tags and record arrivals and departures of all cattle. (Phokoje, 2016). The introduction of the system has however hurdles like computer illiteracy of farmers, time requirements, cost and access to ict sources. Another factor is that ear tags can easily be removed.

Determination of animal location and the mutual contact between animals is essential to investigate the spread of diseases. A reason to have more precise information on a cows location is the wish by the public that cows should be in the pasture, while there is a tendency to keep them indoors. Dairy processors give financial incentives for so called "pasture milk", but this requires auditable means to record the time that cows spent in the pasture. Strict regulations on manure requires that every load of manure is traced and sampled to determine mineral content. It is now under investigation to use NIR technology for nutrient determination. The European Union founded a Food Authenticity Coordination Group (FACG) which will investigate standards which are required and can be validated to determine the authenticity of food. One of the focus products is milk.

Communication of data between intelligent systems.

Figure 1 and the described examples of the different components show a diversity of equipment and services which cannot be delivered at the highest quality by a single source. The services of different parties among which the old established ones and start-ups have to exchange data. A clear example of such an approach is the cooperation of equipment provider Fancom with the service provider The Applied Group. Technology and standards to get this data at the world wide web is already discussed before. Exchange between the different services is de facto based on standard internet technology and one can only discuss on using SOAP/XML based webservices, REST/JSON based ones or as Linked Data by use of RDF and SPARQL. The biggest challenge is the semantics of the data. Linked Open Data provides the mechanisms to publish the meaning and structure of the data, but this does not necessarily mean that this meaning is machine interpretable. And as long as different providers of services find it more efficient to define their own data model instead of spending time to look at proposed standards, it is an illusion to expect that they will specify the mapping of their data to models to those developed by other parties by means of OWL techniques. The level of aggregation of data causes also problems as data which is aggregated by one party cannot be disaggregated when further used. Not only the data definition but also the way they are computed is important for correct interpretation. Take as an example the calculation of behaviour of a cow. How is determined that she is at risk due to a too long resting time. How is lameness computed.

What we see in practise is that platforms are established which will act as data brokers and take care of the mapping of the different data streams. Examples are The Digital Homestead in Australia, InfoBroker developed in the Smart Dairy Farming project in the Netherlands as well as EDI-Circle used for exchange of invoices and several other messages from feed suppliers, dairy companies and the government, to accounting firms and farm management software. In dairy farming it is also the basis for a farm mineral accounting system. Farmers control the flow of data in EDI-Circle with authorisations. Currently this authorisation is done on paper, but a special website (AgriTrust) is under development now that a standard EDI message for authorisations is becoming available. This authorisation system builds trust in (digital) data exchange because it allows farmers to execute the ownership of their data. EDI-Circle is also used by Agriplace a start-up by a Dutch NGO with a sustainability compliance objective. Agriplace offers farmers a platform to share their certification data with the auditing organisations, the certification bodies and the food processors.

Standards

An alternative is the development of standards for data exchange. AgroConnect from the Netherlands is an example of a standards organisation which defines standard messages based on specified data definitions. There is EDI-Pigs to inform breeding organisations on the number of piglets, EDI slaughter to give a feedback on quantity and quality of meat, Data on performance of dairy for breeding organizations, data on transport of manure, movement of animals, data on payment for delivered milk and data on delivered feed. Important international standards are those from ISO on RFID. AgroConnect developed together with Fancom and other companies standard messages for exchange of information among process computers and with advisory systems, which will be proposed as ISO standard. The draft is already implemented by Fancom and The Applied Group.

ICAR also acts as a standards institute for data on milk meters and automatic milking systems.

Open data

Open data is data that can be accessed by anyone. This means that data is online accessible on a known location in a standard digital form which is machine-readable. Relevant for agriculture is: satellite imagery, weather records and predictions, trade statistics, market prices, soil data and data on fertilizers, crop protection products and pharmaceuticals. The big question is however who is going to pay for providing this open data. An obvious partner are governmental organizations. When they pay the majority of the cost to obtain weather data, soil data, satellite data and data for crop protection products, it is little additional cost to make this data available as open data. However, reality shows that laws are required to enforce this, and there is little or no incentive for the organizations to make it available following innovative ICT methods. It is unrealistic to expect that data which requires effort to collect and keep actual is available for free.

Another category of data of importance for Agriculture is coding data or sometimes called reference data. There are lots of organizations establishing coding data like for units, meteorological variables, soil types, language and country codes, etc. The organizations establishing such standards do not all see yet an obligation to make them available as open data. One of them is ISO, which is still used to cover their operating cost by selling standards in a non-machine readable form. There will be companies that have interest in providing data as open data. Either by selling them like Homologa for crop protection products, or because they can sell the products specified by the open data like for example data on bulls to sell sperm.

Hurdles

There are several hurdles to overcome when implementing the described system of advanced sensors and services. One is low understanding of the technology by farmers and dealers. Companies have often problems to find people that can combine domain knowledge with information engineering principles. Companies also struggle with maintaining software versions and keeping them upward compatible. The lack of standards and integration which sometimes results in use of more systems to get a complete overview with often redundant data entry. The end user is confronted with systems that are to say at least not “plug and Play”.

There are also technical hurdles like lack of coverage of telematics in rural areas, unreliable internet and possible power failures. Agriculture is also a “Dirty environment”. There is dust on lenses, rodents that eat cables and ammonia and salts that corrode sensors and electronics. There is also some concern that Big Companies collect farmers data and get control of the operation.

The biggest hurdle is however that benefits must be proven (investigation among farmers by the EU-PLF project). Farmers are made skeptical because claims by some products cannot be met.

Conclusions

Sensors and measurement systems are very helpful to indicate health problems of animals in an early stage. Integration of systems and services of different parties is not a technical problem as solutions are available, but much more an organisational one as it requires parties to synchronise work and say good bye to old legacy systems.

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